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THE IMPORTANCE AND ADVANTAGES OF TRANSITIONING TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article outlines in detail the advantages and importance of international financial reporting standards, their content, objectives, assessment of the impact of international financial reporting standards on the accounting system of Uzbekistan and the comprehensive measures being taken to effectively improve it, and also highlights the effective organization based on the analysis of the comprehensive use of these standards in practice and the latest measures implemented in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the transition to international financial reporting standards.

Keywords: *international financial Reporting standards (IFRS), international accounting standards (IAS), accounting, financial reporting, economic growth, foreign investment, efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the gradual implementation of intensive reforms in introducing international accounting standards in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a regulatory and legal framework has been established to govern the transition to international financial reporting standards. Particularly, in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been officially adopted Presidential Decree No. PD-4611 “On Additional Measures for the Transition to International Financial Reporting Standards”.

Above mentioned Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4611 “On Additional Measures for Transitioning to International Financial Reporting Standards” has initiated a new stage in the transition to IFRS within the country’s accounting system. In accordance with this decree, joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance companies, and large taxpaying legal entities operating

in the country are required to maintain their accounting based on International Financial Reporting Standards.

International Financial Reporting Standards are a separate branch of financial accounting and reporting, a part of financial reporting that studies the conceptual foundations, methodological issues of necessity, the development of international financial reporting standards, their content, interpretation, and application. International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), combined with high quality, provide a set of internationally recognized accounting standards, which, in turn, ensure transparency, accountability and efficiency in financial markets around the world. At the same time, transparency demonstrates the comparability and quality of financial statements, accountability prevents information shortages, and efficiency is used to assess opportunities and risks. It is known from world practice that international financial reporting standards have had a positive impact on the activities of large companies. It should be noted that, these international standards are recognized by almost 146 countries around the world. Therefore, the preparation of financial statements in accordance with international Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in the accounting system is also important for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Globalization has led to the increasing integration of global markets for goods, services, and capital, because of which companies that traditionally depended on financing in their domestic capital markets now have much greater access to debt and equity capital both inside and outside their country. Undoubtedly, one of the main advantages of a single set of international accounting standards on a global scale is that it allows international capital markets to evaluate and compare the activities of companies more meaningfully, profitably, and effectively.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It is emphasized that the application of accounting standards in accordance with international financial reporting standards is an integral part of ensuring the quality of accounting. International financial reporting standards are designed for use in the preparation of general-purpose financial statements, that is, to provide financial information to users who cannot require the organization of the preparation of reports, taking into account specific information needs. Foreign scientists such as Giorgio A. A, Martin B, Walter T, Charles T, David B, Terteleva A.S, Zhdanova A.B, as well as scientists from the Republic of Uzbekistan including Ergasheva Sh.T, Ibragimov A.K, Rizaev N.K, Ibragimova I.R, Norbekov D.E, To'rayev A.N, Rahmonov Sh.Sh, Tashnazarov S, Karimov A.A, Imamova N.M, and others have conducted relevant research in the field related to the effective use and implementation of international financial reporting standards.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

In a market economy, comprehensive economic management is carried out through an accounting system. Thus, accounting in the country's economy is considered as a fundamental sphere. When accounting ensures transparency, efficiency, and reliability, these objectives are achieved through standards, specifically the internationally recognized accounting standards that fulfill this exact purpose. In other words, the comparability, reliability, efficiency, and transparency of financial indicators in a country's economy are primarily determined by international standards.

It should be noted that international Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) differ sharply from national accounting standards. For example, the basic principle of international financial reporting standards is that economic content takes precedence over legal form, and the professional opinion of an accountant in many cases will be crucial. However, national accounting standards place great emphasis on documenting transactions. In addition, financial reporting under International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is used by investors to make investment decisions. And national accounting standards are designed to provide information to tax and regulatory authorities.

International financial reporting standards significantly contribute to solving the following issues:

- comparison of financial statements of enterprises around the world;
- the opportunity to reproduce the financial statements of enterprises by external users from different countries.

Investors are looking for opportunities to diversify and invest around the world, while companies raise capital, conclude deals, or have international operations and branches in many countries. Thus, the advantage of accounting standards over international financial reporting standards is that they solve problems such as the above by providing a set of high-quality, internationally recognized accounting standards that ensure transparency, accountability, and efficiency of financial markets worldwide. In addition, IFRS accounting standards enhance economic efficiency by assisting investors identify opportunities and risks in the global market, thereby improving capital allocation. For enterprises, using a single reliable accounting language reduces the cost of capital and reduces the cost of international financial reporting. Therefore, these IFRS standards offer numerous advantages for the economy of Uzbekistan. Through the implementation of international financial reporting standards, the comparability of financial data within the country's economy is primarily ensured. These standards are considered global benchmarks, recognized as comprehensible and accurate worldwide. Furthermore, due to the comparability principle of international financial reporting standards, countries worldwide can systematize data in a uniform

manner and compare it with one another. Thus, international financial reporting standards are considered as the language of business all over the world.

The purpose of the transition to international financial reporting standards in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to provide correct, reliable and transparent information about the financial activities and condition of the organization while increasing opportunities to attract foreign investment, access to international capital and financial markets.

At present, when economic reforms are being carried out at an accelerated pace in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in all spheres, deep reforms are being carried out in the field of accounting and auditing. As economic reforms are being implemented at an accelerated pace in the Republic of Uzbekistan, profound reforms are also taking place in the field of accounting and auditing, just as in all other sectors. Measures are being taken to apply international financial reporting standards in two directions, the following work has been carried out towards the introduction of international financial reporting standards. Initially, the only organization developing international financial reporting standards in the world is the International Financial Reporting Standards Foundation, with which the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed an agreement, in accordance with International financial reporting standards are officially recognized in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These IFRS documents consist of 62 documents, all of which are officially adopted in the state language and this document is directly used by business entities.

In the process of economic modernization, as we need to transition to international financial reporting standards, it is crucial to not only improve the legislative system in the initial stage but also to train and provide qualified personnel in this field. The number of employees with international accounting certificates is significantly low compared to the number of organizations that need to transition to international financial reporting standards. If an average of three employees are required for each of the more than 2,600 organizations, there would be a need for approximately 8,000 employees with international certificates today. This indicates that there is a shortage of qualified personnel in this field. In Uzbekistan, during the transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), it is necessary to implement methodological support, more specifically, to provide procedural guidance. The purpose of this is to further accelerate the process of transitioning business entities to IFRS and provide them with the necessary opportunities to do so. This methodological support should consist of fundamental guidelines, standards, and regulations for the application of international financial reporting standards. Currently, a chart of accounts and financial reporting forms have been approved for organizations conducting accounting activities based on national

standards. However, in practice, there is no standard chart of accounts or financial reporting templates for organizations that prepare reports based on international financial reporting standards. Therefore, it is advisable to organize methodological support for these organizations as well.

In order to use international financial reporting standards in the Republic of Uzbekistan and, accordingly, to officially recognize the text of the comments, the normative and legal international financial reporting standards have been translated into Uzbek language, containing the conceptual framework of financial reporting, 17 international financial reporting standards, 25 international accounting standards, 15 interpretations of the International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee, and 5 SIC Interpretations also formed.

The main advantages of transitioning to the International financial reporting standards for the country's economy:

- In combination with the fact that business entities can submit financial statements in the same manner as their competitors in foreign countries, it becomes possible to compare the statements;
- Increasing the level of investment attraction as a result of establishing effective partnerships with foreign investors;
- The ability to make accurate forecasts for financial and economic analysts will be increased.
- For shareholders and managers, an objective analysis of the business can provide an opportunity to assess the company's real situation and may become one of the important tools for making management decisions;
- The value of an business entity will increase, and the confidence in the financial and accounting information provided by the enterprise will be higher;
- The IFRS accounting Standards provide a set of high-quality, internationally recognized accounting standards that ensure transparency, accountability and efficiency of financial markets around the world.
- IFRS accounting standards enhance economic efficiency by supporting investors identify opportunities and risks around the world, thereby improving capital allocation. For enterprises, using a single reliable accounting language reduces the cost of capital and reduces the cost of preparing international financial statements.

Research based on the application of international financial reporting standards in practice shows that the decrease in the cost of capital and the improvement in stock prices, as well as trading indicators, are increasing, partly as a result of wider disclosure and comparison of financial and accounting information. However, according to the conducted research, these improvements and positive changes are taking place in countries where strict international standards are observed. Thus, it is not enough to

simply adopt international financial reporting standards and switch to it, the reason is that the creation of identical financial statements is unlikely. In order to achieve maximum comparison, these international standards must be constantly applied in practice, checked by professional specialists and carried out qualitatively.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth emphasizing that today, the transition to International Financial Reporting Standards in the Republic of Uzbekistan is becoming increasingly important in attracting foreign investors and enhancing the level of transparency and accuracy of financial reporting. As a result of our study on this topic during the research process, we have arrived at the following conclusions. The systematization of legislation in the field of accounting, the provision of financial statements based on international standards of accounting and financial reporting, the establishment of measures to apply international standards of financial reporting in established organizations, will increase investment attractiveness on the scale of the Republic of Uzbekistan, effectively systematize the industry, ensure confidence in financial statements, increase the comparability of financial data.

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